

NEW MECHANISMS OF PUBLIC PROCUREMENT

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Abstract. This article talks about new mechanisms of public procurement. The economy of our country is developing from year to year, which is why some proposals have been made to ensure the needs of the state and society, to improve the mechanism of public procurement, and to ensure the openness and transparency of procurement processes.

Key words: procurement, international audit, forensics, digitization.

Today, the economy of our country is developing from year to year, which is of great importance in providing the needs of the state and society, improving the mechanism of public procurement, and ensuring the openness and transparency of procurement processes.

Public procurement has been raised to the level of politics, and the decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated July 2, 2021 "On additional measures to ensure transparency and increase efficiency of public procurement" No. PQ-5171 was adopted. With this decision, all large corporate customers were assigned the tasks of international audit of procurement processes, including the "forensic" task of improving the effectiveness of anti-corruption systems.

In order to ensure the implementation of the decision, international auditing company "Deloitte & Touche" LTD will join the "BIG FOUR" in 2022 in connection with the "forensics" of conducting an international audit of procurement processes of "Uzbekhydroenergo" JSC and system enterprises for the period of 2021, including improving the effectiveness of anti-corruption systems signed a contract with.

"Deloitte & Touche" is an independent audit brand that unites more than ten thousand highly qualified professionals providing services in financial consulting, risk management, tax and related fields.

During the audit, "Deloitte & Touche" LTD presented its final positive conclusion that there were no negative situations such as violations of applicable legal requirements, corruption and conflicts of interest in public procurement processes carried out by the Company. Also, the company specifically recognized that the procurement coordination department of the Society is carrying out

digitization of the procurement process, and the necessary recommendations were given for its further development in the future.

In practice, the set of actions that cause corruption factors is very diverse. One of them is the signing of contracts with a "favorite" company related to a politician or an official, i.e. receiving tangible and intangible benefits. In addition, situations such as the conclusion of transactions between affiliated persons increase the risk of corruption.

Today, on the basis of the recommendations given by the international audit company "Deloitte & Touche" LTD, the procurement coordination department is working on improving the single integrated electronic database of the procurement process of the Society and its system. In a word, "Uzbekhydroenergo" JSC is trying to advance as much as possible in the "digital arms" race, which has become a tradition in the world's leading countries, and significant work is being done in this field.

All the digitization work carried out by the Society is directly supported by the initiative of the Chairman of the Society's Board of Directors, and perhaps without such support the work being carried out would have been carried out much more slowly.

In a word, ensuring the economic security of the society, forming an integrated system aimed at preventing the occurrence of corruption and conflicts of interest, effective vertical and horizontal relations of the society system, as well as strengthening the legitimacy through the introduction of modern working methods are of priority.

It is clear that the wide-ranging reforms implemented by the Society will serve to prevent corruption risks and increase transparency in trade processes. In conclusion, digitization is a long-term, laborious and daily task, but it will lead the way.